

THE PURPOSE AND OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY, ITS LOGIC

Asian international University.

Senior teacher of “ pedagogy and philosophy “
department Gadaeva Munira Mukhammedovna

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mantiq sohasidagi tadqiqotlarning xususiyatlari, mantiqiy va mantiqiy bo'lmagan atamalarning xarakteristikalari, empirik va nazariy mantiqiy atamalarning xususiyatlari, bilimning ilmiy va ilmiy bo'lmaganligining mantiqiy va uslubiy mezonlari yoritilgan.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются особенности исследований в области логики. В работе дается характеристика логических и нелогических терминов, исследуются особенности эмпирических и теоретических логических терминов, приводятся логико-методологические критерии научности и не научности знания.

Annotation: The article discusses the features of research in the field of logic. The work gives characteristics of logical and non-logical terms, examines the features of empirical and theoretical logical terms, and provides logical and methodological criteria for the scientific and non-scientific nature of knowledge.

Ключевые слова: логика / познание / логические термины / нелогические термины / эмпирические логические термины / теоретические логические термины / логико-методологические критерии научности знания

Key words: knowledge / empirical logical terms / theoretical logical terms / logical and methodological criteria of scientific knowledge / logical terms / non-logical terms

The purpose, objective and its logical study of in the 3 period of renaissance. Logic is an integral part of the doctrine of knowledge. It is called formal because it studies the forms of thoughts and thought processes, i.e. structures identified by partial abstraction from the semantic and objective meanings of non-logical terms included in the linguistic expressions by which these thoughts and thinking processes are represented.

There is no clear division of terms into logical and non-logical. There is no doubt that the terms expressed in ordinary language by the words “essence (is)”, “therefore”, “and”, “each”, etc., are logical

It is possible to indicate a common property of these terms: they are used in discussions about various areas of objective and subjective reality. Terms expressed in everyday language by the words “obligatory”, “allowed”, etc., do not have this property, but, nevertheless, they are classified as logical. We will assume that the division of terms into logical and non-logical is established on the basis of agreement.

Part of the abstraction from the semantic and objective meanings of non-logical terms lies in the fact that when identifying logical forms, information about the type of non-logical terms and where there was the same term and where there were different ones is preserved.

Thus, logic is the science of the forms of thoughts and thought processes, as well as the relationships between thoughts and thought processes based on the properties of their logical forms.

The immediate characteristics of research activities are the purpose and objectives of the research. A goal is an idea of a result. When setting a goal, a person imagines what result he intends to get, what this result will be. Outlining the logic of his research, the scientist formulates a number of specific research tasks, which together should give an idea of what needs to be done in order for the goal to be achieved. In one of the works on higher education pedagogy, the goal is outlined as follows: to identify the didactic conditions for the formation of a culture of educational activity of students and to determine the ways of their creation in the process of teaching and educating students.

A sequential series of tasks reflected the logic of the study: to study the state of the culture of students’ educational activities; analyze the concept of “culture of educational activity” and the correspondence of its essence and structure to the content and methods of work to improve the educational activity of students; determine and test in the process of experimental work the didactic conditions for the formation of a learning culture; develop methodological recommendations for teachers on managing the development of a culture of students’ educational activities. Determining the logic, the general path of research is a very important stage of the work. This is the identification of the main steps leading to solving the problem and fulfilling the purpose of the research work. Of course, each problem is specific and requires intuition and creativity from the researcher. However, it is quite possible to indicate the general course of pedagogical research (and also display it graphically),

so that the resulting methodological representation can be used as a certain guideline for research activities, against which one could check one's path and judge the quality of the research as it unfolds.

It is necessary to distinguish between the sensually concrete as a result of the direct perception of real concreteness, and the mentally concrete - the result of reproducing real concreteness in theoretical thinking. Ascent from the abstract to the concrete is both a method of scientific research and a principle that characterizes the direction of the scientific-cognitive process as a whole - the movement from less meaningful to more meaningful knowledge. True concreteness in research is based on abstraction, due to which concrete knowledge appears not as an episodic perception of the whole, but as a living unity of essence and its manifestation, the internal content of an object and the form of its expression. The movement of theoretical thought from the abstract to the concrete in the text of a scientific work that is to be reflected and evaluated can in itself be an indicator of the evidence of this research and thereby its quality. In order to present the generalized logic of pedagogical research in the most concrete form, we depict its progress as a sequence of transitions from an empirical description of pedagogical activity to its reflection in a theoretical form (in theoretical models) and in a normative form (in normative models). The starting points underlying the idea of the logic of pedagogical research boil down to the following. Any pedagogical research is a contribution to the scientific substantiation of practical pedagogical activities. In the system of scientific justification, the connection between the two functions of pedagogy as a science is realized - scientific-theoretical and constructive-technical (normative). Carrying out the first of them, pedagogy studies pedagogical reality in the aspect of reality, i.e. its objectively true reflection, gains knowledge about pedagogical facts, about the essence and laws of the pedagogical process. As a result of the implementation of the constructive-technical function, pedagogy receives knowledge that reflects pedagogical reality in the aspect of what should be: how to plan, implement and improve pedagogical activities. The transition from the reflection of pedagogical reality to its transformation in the structure of scientific justification can be represented as a process of formation of a number of theoretical and normative models of pedagogical reality in their dynamic relationship. Presented in this way, this transition must be reflected in a specific, single pedagogical study. Scientific justification in that case corresponds to its purpose if it

is proactive in relation to pedagogical practice and allows it to be transformed and improved. In order to get ahead and transform the experience of practical pedagogical activity in the right direction, pedagogical science must use all the wealth of human culture, generalized practice, social experience in general, and the reflection of this experience in scientific knowledge. This requirement also applies to the construction of theoretical and normative models in a single pedagogical study. The main feature of a model of existence - a theoretical model is that it represents some clear, fixed connection of elements, presupposes a certain structure that reflects the internal, essential relations of reality. The model of what should be, the normative model, like the theoretical model, is idealized and generalized. It does not constitute a direct project, a “scenario” of pedagogical activity, but is only a subsequently implemented prototype of such projects. Such a model provides a general idea of what needs to be done to achieve better results. The work as a whole is of an applied nature. Its theoretical part concretizes the existing ideas in pedagogy about the relationship between teaching, upbringing and development. In the course of such specification, the statement is formulated that mental education cannot be considered complete and sufficient if as a result only mental development is achieved and only cognitive interest is formed. A person can have a cognitive interest, but at the same time be morally ill-mannered, selfish towards comrades, towards other people, etc. Mental education in its integrity and completeness is formed by a wide range of relationships of the student to himself, to his own activities, to other students, to teachers, to people in general.

Research logic is an important tool for scientific research. It helps to structure and systematize knowledge, and also develops critical thinking and analytical skills. The purpose of the research logic is to achieve objectivity and reliability of the research results. The basic principles of research logic include logical consistency, clarity and precision of statements, and testability and validity of arguments. The logic of research is closely related to other sciences, such as philosophy, mathematics and psychology. Applications of inquiry logic can be found in various fields, from scientific research to everyday life. It is important to develop logical thinking skills and apply them in your activities to achieve successful results.

References:

1. A country where children are healthy has a great future: President Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.Mirziyoev// Nar. word. – 2017. – 6 Jan.
2. Mirziyoyev. Sh.M. Together we will build a free, democratic and the prosperous state of Uzbekistan. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2016. - 56 p.
3. Kraevsky V.V. The quality of pedagogy and the methodological culture of the teacher // Master: Independent scientific and pedagogical journal. 1991. No. 1.
4. Polonsky V.M. Evaluation of the quality of scientific and pedagogical research. M., 1987.
4. Skatkin M.N. Methodology and methods of pedagogical research (To help the novice researcher). M., 1986. Internet sites:
5. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). XXI ASR KÓNIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN TA'LIMNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI. PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES AND TEACHING METHODS, 3(26), 93-96
6. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). XXI ASR KÓNIKMALARINI SHAKLLANTIRISHDA INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN TA'LIMNING MUAMMO VA YECHIMLARI. World scientific research journal, 20(1), 135-138.
7. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). INNOVATSION TEXNOLOGIYARNI O'ZLASHTIRISHDA TALABALARNING KREATIVLIK SALOHİYATINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING AHAMIYATI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 21(3), 3-6.
8. GADAYEVA, M. M. INTEGRATSION TA'LIMDA MANTIQUIY VA TANQIDIY TAFAKKURNING PEDAGOGIK-PSIXOLOGIK ASOSLARI. PSIXOLOGIYA Учредители: Бухарский государственный университет, (2), 60-64.
9. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). INNOVATSION TALIM-BUYUK KELAJAK POYDEVORI. World scientific research journal, 17(1), 74-76.
10. Muxamedovna, G. M. (2023). UCHINCHI RENESANS DAVRIDA AJDODLARIMIZ MEROSINI ORGANISH ORQALI INTEGRATSION TA'LIMNI YANADA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH TAMOYILLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 22(1), 35-38.

11. Мухамедовна, G. M. (2023). KREATIV YONDASHUV ASOSIDA DIDAKTIK MATERIALLAR YARATISH MEKANIZMLARI. ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ НАУКА И ИННОВАЦИОННЫЕ ИДЕИ В МИРЕ, 21(3), 12-14.
12. Бозорова, P. Ш. (2022). “Меър” тушунчаси: фалсафий таҳлил. Science and Education, 3(4), 1312-1320.
13. Bozorova, R. (2021, September). Methods and Means of Cultivating Kindness iIn the Family of the Uzbek People. In " ONLINE-CONFERENCES" PLATFORM (pp. 43-44).
14. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PSIXOLOGIYA YO ‘NALISHIDA TAHSIL OLAYOTGAN TALABALARGA SPSS YORDAMIDA MATEMATIK USULLARNI O ‘RGATISHNING METODIK USULLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 323-326.
15. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PYTHON INSTRUMENTLARI BILAN KATTA MA’LUMOTLARNI QAYTA ISHLASH. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 320-322.
16. Jalolov, T. S., & Usmonov, A. U. (2021). “AQLLI ISSIQXONA” BOSHQARISH TIZIMINI MODELLASHTIRISH VA TADQIQ QILISH. Экономика и социум, (9 (88)), 74-77.
17. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023). Capabilities of SPSS Software in High Volume Data Processing Testing. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 82-86.
18. Sadriddinovich, J. T. (2023, November). IDENTIFYING THE POSITIVE EFFECTS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL AND SOCIAL WORK FACTORS BETWEEN INDIVIDUALS AND DEPARTMENTS THROUGH SPSS SOFTWARE. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH CONFERENCE (Vol. 2, No. 18, pp. 150-153).
19. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). TEACHING THE BASICS OF PYTHON PROGRAMMING. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
20. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). Solving Complex Problems in Python. American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769), 1(9), 481-484.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-1, Issue-12

21. Jalolov, T. S. (2023). PEDAGOGICAL-PSYCHOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF DATA PROCESSING USING THE SPSS PROGRAM. INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENTS AND RESEARCH IN EDUCATION, 2(23), 220-223.
22. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PYTHON (PYTORCH). Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research , 1(3), 123-126.
23. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ADVANTAGES OF DJANGO FEMWORKER. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).
24. Tursunbek Sadriddinovich Jalolov. (2023). ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE PYTHON (PYTORCH). Oriental Journal of Academic and Multidisciplinary Research , 1(3), 123-126.
25. Ikromova, S. (2023). INTERPRETATION OF THE PSYCHOLOGICAL SAFETY FACTOR IN RELATION TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN ADOLESCENTS. Modern Science and Research, 2(9), 390-394.
26. Ikromova, S. (2023). CONCEPT OF IDEOLOGY AND FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY IN YOUTH STUDENTS. Modern Science and Research, 2(6), 1223-1226.
27. Ikromova, S. (2023). FORMATION OF IDEOLOGICAL IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE INFORMATION IN TEENAGERS. Modern Science and Research, 2(5), 1009-1014.
28. Ikromova, S. A. (2022). MILLIY VA DINIY QADRIYATLARNING INSON TARBIYASIDAGI O'RNI. Экономика и социум, (12-2 (103)), 675-678.
29. Ikromova, S. A. (2023). SHAXS OG 'ISHGAN XULQINING KO 'RINISHLARI VA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARNING KO 'RINISHLARI. Educational Research in Universal Sciences, 2(10), 528-532.
30. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). YOSHLARDA DESTRUKTIV G'OYALARGA QARSHI IMMUNITET HOSIL QILISH OMILLARI.
31. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). TALABA YOSHLARDA MAFKURA TUSHUNCHASI VA MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITETNI SHAKLLANTIRISH.

ISSN (E): 2181-4570 ResearchBib Impact Factor: 6,4 / 2023 SJIF(2023)-3,778 Volume-1, Issue-12

32. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). O'SMIRLARDA DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH.

33. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). DESTRUKTIV AXBOROTLARGA NISBATAN MAFKURAVIY IMMUNITET SHAKLLANTIRISH IJTIMOY MUAMMO SIFATIDA. Barqaror Taraqqiyot va Rivojlanish Tamoyillari, 1(6), 26-29.

34. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). MILLIY HARAKATLI O'YINLARNING BOLALAR TARBIYASIDAGI IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI.

35. Sitara Akbarovna Ikromova. (2023). Formation of Ideological Immunity to Destructive Information. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(9), 50–54.

36. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Study of the Formation of Ideological Immunity By Foreign and Russian Researchers. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(9), 235-239.

37. Akbarovna, I. S. (2023). Adolescence during Destructive Behavior Appearances the Problem Learning Condition. Intersections of Faith and Culture: American Journal of Religious and Cultural Studies (2993-2599), 1(9), 105-109.

38. Ikromova, S. A. FACTORS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF IMMUNITY TO DESTRUCTIVE IDEAS IN ADOLESCENTS.

39. Ikromova Sitara Akbarovna. (2023). RESEARCH METHODS OF YOUTH PSYCHOLOGY. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(12).

40. Immunity to Destructive Information in Adolescents. American Journal of Public Diplomacy and International Studies (2993-2157), 1(10), 119–122.

